

HEAd and neCK TumOR (HECKTOR) Lesion Segmentation, Diagnosis and Prognosis using Multimodal Data : Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

HEAd and neCK TumOR (HECKTOR) Lesion Segmentation, Diagnosis and Prognosis using Multimodal Data

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

HECKTOR 2025

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Head and Neck (H&N;) cancers are among the most common cancers worldwide (5th leading cancer by incidence) (Parkin et al. 2005). Radiotherapy combined with cetuximab has been established as a standard treatment (Bonner et al. 2010). However, locoregional failures remain a major challenge, occurring in up to 40% of patients in the first two years after the treatment (Chajon et al. 2013). Recently, several radiomics studies based on Positron Emission Tomography (PET) and Computed Tomography (CT) imaging were proposed to better identify patients with a worse prognosis in a non-invasive fashion and by exploiting already available images such as these acquired for diagnosis and treatment planning (Vallières et al. 2017),(Bogowicz et al. 2017), (Castelli et al. 2017). By focusing on metabolic and morphological tissue properties, PET and CT modalities include complementary and synergistic information for cancerous lesion segmentation and tumor characteristics potentially relevant for patient outcome prediction, in addition to usual clinical variables (e.g., age, gender, treatment modality, etc.). Modern image analysis (radiomics, machine, and deep learning) methods must be developed and, more importantly, rigorously evaluated in order to extract and leverage this information. Although highly promising, these methods were validated on relatively small cohorts of patients. Further validation on larger, multicentric cohorts (e.g., >1000 patients, >5 centers) is required to ensure an adequate ratio between the number of variables and observations to avoid overestimating the generalization performance.

In 2020, we organized the first HECKTOR challenge to offer an opportunity for participants working on 3D segmentation algorithms to develop automatic bi-modal approaches for the segmentation of H&N; primary tumors (GTVp) in PET/CT scans, focusing on oropharyngeal cancers.

In the 2021 edition, the scope of the challenge was expanded by proposing the segmentation task on a larger population (adding patients from a new clinical center for a total of 325 cases) as well as adding a second task (split into two subtasks: with or without reference contours), namely the prediction of Progression-Free Survival (PFS). In 2022, the scope was expanded even further by increasing the complexity of the segmentation task (no bounding box provided, and lymph nodes (GTVn) had to be delineated in addition to the primary tumor), adding data from 3 new centers (total of 883/828 cases for Tasks 1 and 2 respectively) to ensure an entirely unseen test set (all test data of 2021 was moved to the training set of 2022), and switching to the prediction of Recurrence-Free Survival (RFS).

For the 2025 edition, we propose the following updates and additions to improve the clinical relevance, increase the interest of competitors, and add novelty:

1) All data included in the 2022 edition (~850 patients) will be updated as much as possible, especially regarding the previously missing clinical information, such as the HPV status, which is highly clinically relevant, and the follow-up (to increase the duration of follow-up and potentially the number of recorded recurrence events). It will constitute the training set of 2025.

2) Four new cohorts (1 multicentric, 2 French, 1 Swiss) joined the consortium and will provide 4 entirely new cohorts of patients, which will constitute a new, previously unseen test set (total of ~400 patients). The 2025 database should, therefore, include more than 1500 patients.

3) The segmentation task (Task 1) will be the same as in 2022 but the evaluation will be refined using more appropriate metrics to differentiate better algorithms' ability to detect multiple distinct lesions in addition to segmenting them.

4) Regarding the outcome prediction task, it will be split into a diagnostic task (new Task 3) with high clinical relevance, i.e. the prediction of the HPV status from images and clinical data, in addition to the RFS prediction (Task 2, same as in 2022), which will be expanded by providing updated clinical information (see point 1 above), and dose maps (+ dosimetry CT) of the radiotherapy planning as an added information channel to include in the prediction models, for an estimated subset of 650 patients.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Head and Neck cancer, automatic segmentation, radiomics, PET/CT, multimodal, outcome prediction

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

We introduce several updates for the 2025 HECKTOR challenge to enhance clinical relevance and competitor engagement. The training set will consist of the updated 2022 dataset (~850 patients), now including previously

missing clinical data, such as HPV status and extended follow-up. Additionally, four new cohorts (1 multicentric, 2 French, 1 Swiss) will provide a novel test set (~400 patients), increasing the total database to over 1500 patients. Task 1, focused on lesion segmentation, will include refined evaluation metrics to assess the detection and segmentation of multiple lesions. A new diagnostic task (Task 3) will predict HPV status, complementing the expanded outcome prediction task (Task 2), which now incorporates updated clinical data, radiotherapy dose maps, and dosimetry CT for ~650 patients. We estimate that the test set will consist of 80% HPV-positive cases and 20% HPV-negative cases. These innovations aim to advance clinical and technical insights in head and neck cancer research.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

Task 1: Provide fully automated detection and delineation of both primary tumor volumes and involved lymph nodes in the multimodal FDG PET and CT images. The main clinical application is for subsequent tasks such as radiotherapy treatment planning or modeling including features from the delineated lesions. Evaluated based on a metric combining detection and segmentation since the number of lesions is not known a priori. This year's challenge will focus on combining F1-score to prioritize detection instead of just segmentation. The ranking is based on a combination of the rankings in each metric, from lowest to highest, and the highest value wins.

Task 2: Provide a fully automated prediction of the risk of recurrence (recurrence free survival) based on the multimodal FDG PET/CT images, the available clinical information, and the radiotherapy planning dose maps associated with the dosimetry CT (using all or only parts of the available information at the participants discretion). Evaluated based on the C-index, ranking from the lowest to the highest C-index, highest value wins.

Task 3: Provide a fully automated diagnosis of the HPV status (positive or negative) based on the multimodal FDG PET/CT images and the available clinical information (using all or only parts of the available information at the participants discretion). Evaluated based on the balanced accuracy (BAcc), ranking from the lowest to the highest BAcc, highest value wins. In case of ties, highest specificity wins.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

N/A

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Half day

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

Given that the challenge consists of three tasks, we expect to dedicate around an hour per task to present the results of the top participants.

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

Based on previous years' participation (17 teams in 2020, 32 teams in 2021, and 38 in 2022 submitting results), we can reasonably expect 30-50 teams. This is a conservative estimate, given that participants will submit Docker containers to this year's challenge.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

We plan to coordinate a publication (overview paper) describing the challenge results. A journal paper will be submitted to MedIA summarizing the results and outcomes of the challenge and carrying out several post-challenge analyses, such as low data regime evaluations, sub-cohorts analyses, etc.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

The platform used for the online challenge will be Grand Challenge (<https://grand-challenge.org/>).

Standard presentation equipment will be needed: projector, computer, loudspeakers, and microphones.

TASK 1: Lesions detection and segmentation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Provide fully automated detection and delineation of primary tumor volumes and involved lymph nodes in the multimodal FDG PET and CT images. The main clinical application is for subsequent radiotherapy treatment planning or modeling tasks, including features from the delineated lesions. Evaluated based on a metric combining detection and segmentation since the number of lesions is unknown a priori. This year's challenge will focus on combining F1 score to prioritize detection instead of just segmentation. The ranking is based on a combination of the rankings in each metric, from lowest to highest, and the highest value wins.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Head and Neck cancer, automatic segmentation, PET/CT, multimodal

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

- Numan Saeed: Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- Muhammad Ridzuan: Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- Shahad Hardan: Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- Salma Hassan: Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- Darya Taratynova: Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- Ufaq Khan: Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- Umair Nawaz: Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- Yutong Xie: Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- Mohammad Yaqub: Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- Arman Rahmim: BC Cancer Research Institute, Vancouver, Canada
- Fereshteh Yousefirizi: BC Cancer Research Institute, Vancouver, Canada
- Adrien Depeursinge: Institute of Information Systems, University of Applied Sciences Western Switzerland (HES-SO), Sierre, Switzerland and CHUV
- Vincent Andrearczyk: Institute of Information Systems, University of Applied Sciences Western Switzerland (HES-SO), Sierre, Switzerland
- Mathieu Hatt: LaTIM, INSERM, UMR 1101, Univ Brest, Brest, France
- Isaac Shiri: Bern University Hospital

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

- Vincent Andrearczyk: vincent.andrearczyk@hevs.ch
- Numan Saeed: numan.saeed@mbzuai.ac.ae
- Fereshteh Yousefirizi: frizi@bccrc.ca
- Umair Nawaz: umair.nawaz@mbzuai.ac.ae

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

Challenge associated with MICCAI 2025

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

2025 will be updated later on grand-challenge (2022 website: <https://hecktor.grand-challenge.org/>)

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Participants may use additional public data to extend the provided dataset for training the algorithm chosen for ranking, but the use of private data (e.g., from their own institutions) is strictly prohibited. Similarly, models pretrained on private datasets are not permitted. This policy ensures a fair comparison among all participating methods. However, participants may use both public and private data for scientific publication purposes, provided they explicitly disclose this in their submitted manuscripts and include results obtained using only the provided HECKTOR2025 data to highlight any potential differences.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

Award for the best-ranked team, conditioned on a paper submission reporting the details of the methods. In the event that teams achieve identical metric scores or statistical analysis reveals no significant performance differences between top-ranking teams, we will equitably divide the awards among those teams. This approach ensures fairness while preserving the competitive spirit of the challenge and recognizes equivalent technical achievements.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

The results and winner will be announced publicly.

Once participants submit their results on the test set to the challenge organizers via the challenge website, they will be considered fully vested in the challenge, so that their performance results (without identifying the participant unless permission is granted) will become part of any presentations, publications, or subsequent analyses derived from the Challenge at the discretion of the organizers.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

The participating teams are encouraged to publish their results in the LNCS proceedings of the challenge (following the MICCAI proceedings timeline and subject to acceptance). Participants can submit their results elsewhere when citing the overview paper, and (if so) no embargo will be applied.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

The participating teams will submit segmentation outputs via grand-challenge.org. We will provide a link to the submission instructions.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

The task submission is divided into 1+2 phases: sanity check, validation (Phase 1), and testing (Phase 2).

The sanity check consists of 3 images. Its purpose is to ensure that the participating teams are familiar with the

Grand Challenge platform and that their dockers run without errors. All teams will make their submission to the sanity check phase and will receive feedback on their errors.

The validation phase (Phase 1) consists of about 50 images. All teams will submit 2 working dockers from the sanity check to the validation phase. Only the top 15 teams, as ranked by the evaluation metric and displayed on the public validation leaderboard, with valid submissions will proceed to Phase 2.

The testing phase (Phase 2) consists of about 400 images. The teams will choose 1 of 2 dockers from the validation phase to be submitted to the testing phase. The official ranking of the teams will be based on the testing phase. We will request that each run must be specifically identified and described in the team report accompanying the submissions.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

- 1) Release of the Training Cases: 15th May 2025
- 2) Validation Submission: 10th July to 10th August 2025
- 3) Selection & Announcement of the Top 15 Teams: 10th August to 14th August 2025
- 4) Testing Submission: opens 15th August 2025, closes 1st September 2025
- 5) Final Report Submission: 8th September 2025
- 6) Announcement of the Top 5 Teams: 15th September 2025
- 7) Associated Workshop Days: Either 23rd or 27th September 2025

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

We indicate the answers for the cases of the different centers.

- Montreal, CA: CHUM, CHUS, HGJ, HMR (train): The ethics approval was granted by the Research Ethics Committee of McGill University Health Center (Protocol Number: MM-JGH-CR15-50).
- Lausanne, CH: CHUV (train): The ethics approval was obtained from the Commission cantonale (VD) d'éthique de la recherche sur l'être humain (CER-VD) with protocol number: 2018-01513.
- Poitiers, FR: CHUP (train): The fully anonymized data originates from patients who consent to use their data for research purposes.
- Houston: MDA (train): The ethics approval was obtained from the University of Texas MD Anderson Cancer

Center Institutional Review Board with protocol number RCR03-0800.

- Zürich, CH, USZ (train): The ethics approval was related to the clinical trial NCT01435252 entitled "A Phase II Study In Patients With Advanced Head And Neck Cancer Of Standard Chemoradiation And Add-On Cetuximab."
- Rouen, FR: CHB (train): The fully anonymized data originates from patients who consent to use their data for research purposes.
- Brest, FR: CHUB (test): The fully anonymized data originates from patients who consent to use their data for research purposes.
- Nantes, FR: CHUN (test): The fully anonymized data originates from patients who consent to use their data for research purposes.
- GORTEC (test): The fully anonymized data originates from patients who consent to use their data for research purposes.
- Geneve, CH: HUG (test): The fully anonymized data originates from patients who consent to use their data for research purposes.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The code to produce the results and ranking will be made available on our GitHub repository. Link to the full code and documentation will be added to the challenge page.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Although the participating teams will be strongly encouraged to disclose or share their code, it will remain optional.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The challenge is funded by the BioMedIA Lab at the Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, and partly funded by Society of Nuclear Medicine and Molecular Imaging (SNMMI) AI task force. Companies who funded HECKTOR 2021 and 2022 such as Aquilab, and Bioemtech will be contacted to sponsor the challenge. Additional companies will also be contacted to secure funding.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

The participating algorithms target automated detection and delineation of lesions.

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation

- Tracking

Segmentation, Detection

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Patients received for initial staging of oropharyngeal H&N; cancer. The clinical goals are two-fold; the automatically detected and segmented lesions can be used as inputs for (i) the treatment planning in radiotherapy, (ii) further investigations to predict clinical outcomes such as recurrence-free survival (see Task 2) and tumor aggressiveness (see Task 3).

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Patients with histologically proven oropharyngeal H&N; cancer who underwent (chemo)radiotherapy treatment with curative intent.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

FDG-PET/CT scans (both functional FDG PET and low-dose CT modalities acquired with the same multimodal scanner are considered).

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The information on image data will include clinical center, scanner information, DICOM meta-data including acquisition parameters and reconstruction algorithms.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

The patient information will include center, age, gender, tobacco and alcohol consumption, performance status, treatment (radiotherapy only or chemoradiotherapy, and M stage (T and N stage will not be provided as it informs on lymph nodes status which is part of the goal of Task 1). HPV status will be provided for the training set but not the testing set (since it will be the ground-truth of Task 3). There are missing values for some patients, although an effort will be carried out by each clinical center to update the information as much as possible.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary,

differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The data originates from FDG-PET and low-dose non-contrast-enhanced CT images (acquired with combined PET/CT scanners) of the H&N; region.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm target is the H&N; oropharyngeal cancer primary Gross Tumor Volume (GTVp) and lymph node gross tumor volume (GTVn) lesions.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The device(s) used to acquire the training and testing images are listed in the following for the different centers .

- HGJ: A hybrid PET/CT GE Discovery ST
- CHUS: A hybrid PET/CT PhilipsGXL 16.
- HMR: A hybrid PET/CT GE Discovery STE
- CHUM: A hybrid PET/CT GE Discovery STE
- CHUV: A hybrid PET/CT GE Discovery D690 TOF
- CHUP: A hybrid PET/CT Siemens Biograph mCT 40 ToF.
- MDA: Multiple hybrid PET/CT GE devices: Discovery HR, Discovery RX, Discovery ST, Discovery STE
- USZ: Multiple hybrid PET/CT GE devices: Discovery HR, Discovery RX, Discovery STE, Discovery LS, Discovery 690
- CHB: A hybrid PET/CT GE710.
- CHUN: A hybrid PET/CT Siemens mCT 64 vision
- CHUB: Multiple hybrid PET/CT scanner devices: Philips GEMINI, Siemens Biograph, Siemens Biograph Vision
- HUG: A hybrid PET/CT Siemens Biograph 64 True Point scanner
- GORTEC: Multiple hybrid PET/CT scanner devices

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

1) HGJ:

For the PET portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median of 584 MBq (range: 368-715) was injected intravenously. After a 90-minute uptake period of rest, patients were imaged with the PET/CT imaging system. Imaging acquisition of the head and neck was performed using multiple bed positions with a median of 300 s (range: 180-420) per bed position. Attenuation-corrected images were reconstructed using an ordered subset expectation maximization (OSEM) iterative algorithm and a span (axial mash) of 5. The FDG-PET slice thickness resolution was 3.27 mm for all patients, and the median in-plane resolution was $3.52 \times 3.52 \text{ mm}^2$ (range: 3.52-4.69). For the CT portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, an energy of 140 kVp with an exposure of 12 mAs was used. The CT slice thickness resolution was 3.75 mm, and the median in-plane resolution was $0.98 \times 0.98 \text{ mm}^2$ for all patients.

2) CHUS:

For the PET portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median of 325 MBq (range: 165-517) was injected intravenously. After a 90-minute uptake period of rest, patients were imaged with the PET/CT imaging system. Imaging acquisition of the head and neck was performed using multiple bed positions with a median of 150 s (range: 120-151) per bed position. Attenuation-corrected images were reconstructed using a LOR-RAMLA iterative algorithm. The FDG-PET slice thickness resolution was 4 mm, and the median in-plane resolution was $4 \times 4 \text{ mm}^2$ for all patients. For the CT portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median energy of 140 kVp (range: 12-140) with a median exposure of 210 mAs (range: 43-250) was used. The median CT slice thickness resolution was 3 mm (range: 2-5,) and the median in-plane resolution was $1.17 \times 1.17 \text{ mm}^2$ (range: 0.68-1.17).

3) HMR:

For the PET portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median of 475 MBq (range: 227-859) was injected intravenously. After a 90-minute uptake period of rest, patients were imaged with the PET/CT imaging system. Imaging acquisition of the head and neck was performed using multiple bed positions with a median of 360 s (range: 120-360) per bed position. Attenuation-corrected images were reconstructed using an ordered subset expectation maximization (OSEM) iterative algorithm and a median span (axial mash) of 5 (range: 3-5). The FDG-PET slice thickness resolution was 3.27 mm for all patients, and the median in-plane resolution was $3.52 \times 3.52 \text{ mm}^2$ (range: 3.52-5.47). For the CT portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median energy of 140 kVp (range: 120-140) with a median exposure of 11 mAs (range: 5-16) was used. The CT slice thickness resolution was 3.75 mm for all patients, and the median in-plane resolution was $0.98 \times 0.98 \text{ mm}^2$ (range: 0.98-1.37).

4) CHUM:

For the PET portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median of 315 MBq (range: 199-3182) was injected intravenously. After a 90-minute uptake period of rest, patients were imaged with the PET/CT imaging system. Imaging acquisition of the head and neck was performed using multiple bed positions with a median of 300 s (range: 120-420) per bed position. Attenuation-corrected images were reconstructed using an ordered subset expectation maximization (OSEM) iterative algorithm and a median span (axial mash) of 3 (range: 3-5). The median FDG-PET slice thickness resolution was 4 mm (range: 3.27-4), and the median in-plane resolution was $4 \times 4 \text{ mm}^2$ (range: 3.52-5.47). For the CT portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median energy of 120 kVp (range: 120-140) with a median exposure of 350 mAs (range: 5-350) was used. The median CT slice thickness resolution was 1.5 mm (range: 1.5-3.75,) and the median in-plane resolution was $0.98 \times 0.98 \text{ mm}^2$ (range: 0.98-1.37).

5) CHUV:

The patients fasted at least 4 hours before the injection of 4 Mbq/kg of (18F)-FDG (Flucis). Blood glucose levels were checked before injecting (18F)-FDG. If not contra-indicated, intravenous contrast agents were administered before CT scanning. After a 60-minute uptake period of rest, patients were imaged with the PET/CT imaging system. First, a CT (120 kV, 80 mA, 0.8-s rotation time, slice thickness 3.75 mm) was performed from the base of the skull to the mid-thigh. PET scanning was performed immediately after the acquisition of the CT. Images were acquired from the base of the skull to the mid-thigh (3 min/bed position). PET images were reconstructed by using an ordered-subset expectation maximization iterative reconstruction (OSEM) (two iterations, 28 subsets) and an iterative fully 3D (DiscoveryST). CT data were used for attenuation calculation.

6) CHUP:

PET/CT acquisition began after 6 hours of fasting and 60 ± 5 min after injection of 3 MBq/kg of 18F-FDG (421 ± 98 MBq, range 220-695 MBq). Non-contrast-enhanced, non-respiratory gated (free breathing) CT images were acquired for attenuation correction (120 kVp, Care Dose® current modulation system) with an in-plane resolution of 0.853×0.853 mm² and a 5 mm slice thickness. PET data were acquired using 2.5 minutes per bed position routine protocol, and images were reconstructed using a CT-based attenuation correction and the OSEM-TrueX-TOF algorithm (with time-of-flight and spatial resolution modeling, 3 iterations and 21 subsets, 5 mm 3D Gaussian post-filtering, voxel size $4 \times 4 \times 4$ mm³).

7) MDA:

For the PET portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median of 401 MBq (range: 327-266) was injected intravenously. After a 90-minute uptake period of rest, patients were imaged with the PET/CT imaging system. Image acquisition of the head and neck was performed using multiple bed positions with a median of 180 s (range: 90-300) per bed position. Attenuation-corrected images were reconstructed using an ordered subset expectation maximization (OSEM) iterative algorithm (2 iterations, 18-24 subsets, 5mm Gaussian filter). The median FDG-PET slice thickness was 3.27 mm (range: 2.99-5), and the median in-plane resolution was 5.46×5.46 mm² (range: 2.73×2.73 - 5.46×5.46). For the CT portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median energy of 120 kVp (range: 100-140) with a median exposure of 185 mAs (range: 10-397) was used. The median CT slice thickness resolution was 3.75mm (range: 2.99-5), and the median in-plane resolution was 0.98×0.98 mm² (range: 0.48×0.48 - 2.734×2.734).

8) USZ:

For PET imaging, an activity of 178–513 MBq was administered intravenously 1h prior to the scan and after measuring blood sugar level. In the retrospective cohort, 2D or 3D iterative image reconstruction was used, whereas the images of the validation cohort were reconstructed with a 3D algorithm.

9) CHB:

Head and neck PET-CT images were acquired on a GE710 PET-CT device (General Electric, Milwaukee, USA) 90 minutes (± 5 min) after injecting approximately 3 MBq/kg of FDG. PET and CT acquisition parameters were adapted to the patient's habitus with the patient in the radiotherapy treatment position with a contention mask. For the unenhanced CT portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, an energy of 120 kVp with an exposure of 25 mAs was used. Attenuation-corrected images were reconstructed using an ordered subset expectation maximization (OSEM) iterative algorithm (VPFX, 2 iterations, and 23 subsets) and a span (axial mash) of 5. The FDG-PET slice thickness

resolution was 3.27 mm for all patients, and the median in-plane resolution was $2.73 \times 2.73 \text{ mm}^2$. The CT slice thickness resolution was 2.5 mm, and the median in-plane resolution was $0.98 \times 0.98 \text{ mm}^2$ for all patients.

10) CHUN:

After 6h fasting; 3MBq/kg; Acquisition 60 min post-injection; contrast agent if possible, acquisition steps adapted to patient's morphology

Siemens Biograph mCT: Data were reconstructed using the 3D ordinary Poisson ordered subset expectation maximization algorithm with point spread function recovery and time-of-flight information. The reconstruction parameters were 3 iterations, 21 subsets with a 2-mm full width at half maximum (FWHM) Gaussian post-filtering (voxel size $4 \times 4 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$). Low-dose CT 3D was acquired for attenuation and scatter correction, with or without intravenous contrast enhancement, and automatic mA according to the patient's weight.

Siemens Biograph Vision 450: Data were reconstructed using the 3D ordinary Poisson ordered subset expectation maximization algorithm with point spread function recovery and time-of-flight information. The reconstruction parameters were 4 iterations and 5 subsets with a 3-mm FWHM Gaussian post-filtering for the Biograph Vision 450 (voxel size $1.65 \times 1.65 \times 1.65 \text{ mm}^3$). Low-dose CT 3D was acquired for attenuation and scatter correction, with or without intravenous contrast enhancement, and automatic mA according to the patient's weight.

11) HUG:

After fasting for 6h, all patients had a single [^{18}F]FDG injection, followed by a PET/MRI and a subsequent PET/CT scan. A mean dose of $373 \pm 28 \text{ MBq}$ [^{18}F]FDG was injected intravenously into all patients before the PET/MRI examination was started. During the time necessary for radiotracer uptake, a dedicated MRI of the HN region (T2-weighted, diffusion-weighted, and T1-weighted sequences before and after iv. administration of a gadolinium-based contrast material), followed by total body MRI sequences was performed. The total body MRI sequences (see below) were used for attenuation correction, lesion detection, anatomic localization, and lesion characterization. Afterward, a whole-body PET was acquired on the PET/MRI system. The patient was then transferred to the PET/CT scanner, and no additional [^{18}F]FDG was injected. PET/CT images were acquired on a Biograph 64 True Point scanner (Siemens Healthcare, Erlangen, Germany). The standard dose CT scan used for attenuation correction and diagnosis (with soft tissue, bone, and lung windows) had the following parameters: 120kVp, 180mAs, pitch = 1.2, collimation = 24×1.5 , 1 s per rotation, reconstructed CT slice thickness = 2 mm, reconstruction interval = 1.5 mm. PET data acquisition was started $120 \pm 21 \text{ min}$ after injection of [^{18}F]FDG with a total of 8–9 bed positions. The delay between the end of the PET acquisition on the PET/MRI machine and the start of the PET acquisition on the PET/CT machine was, on average, 26 min. No iodine-based iv. contrast material was administered because: (1) according to the ESUR guidelines, for patients with a normal or moderately reduced GFR, there should be $\geq 4 \text{ h}$ between injections of gadolinium- and iodine-based contrast agents [25]; (2) current guidelines for PET/CT do not recommend the routine use of iv. iodine-based contrast in all PET/CT examinations. The AWOSEM iterative reconstruction algorithm (4 iterations, 8 subsets, voxel size = $4 \times 4 \times 5 \text{ mm}^3$) was applied for PET reconstruction. Standardized uptake values (SUVs) were calculated separately for PET/MRI and PET/CT according to the standard formula.

12) CHUB: Details to collect (standard clinical protocol)

13) GORTEC: Details to collect (standard clinical protocol)

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

These are the list of centers that are confirmed:

- HGJ: Hôpital général juif, Montréal, CA
- CHUS: Centre hospitalier universitaire de Sherbrooke, Sherbrooke, CA
- HMR: Hôpital Maisonneuve-Rosemont, Montréal, CA
- CHUM: Centre hospitalier de l'Université de Montréal, Montréal, CA
- CHUV: Centre Hospitalier Universitaire Vaudois, CH
- CHUP: Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Poitiers, FR
- CHUN: Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Nantes, FR
- HUG: Hôpitaux Universitaires de Genève, CH
- GORTEC: Multiple French/Swiss centers, details currently being collected

These centers were included in the 2022 edition and have shown interest in joining the 2025 challenge, but we are waiting for the final approvals:

- MDA: MD Anderson Cancer Center, Houston, Texas, USA
- CHB: Centre Henri Becquerel, Rouen, FR
- USZ: UniversitätsSpital Zürich, CH
- CHUB: Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Brest, FR

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

None.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Training and testing cases represent one 3D FDG-PET volume registered with a 3D CT volume of the head and neck region, as well as contours with the annotated ground truth lesions (only available for training cases to the participating teams). The labels will have three values: background with the value 0, primary Gross Tumor Volumes (GTVp) with the value 1, and nodal Gros Tumor Volumes (GTVn) with the value 2 (in case of several lymph nodes, they are considered all with the same label). Patient information including center, age, gender, tobacco and alcohol consumption, performance status, HPV status, treatment (radiotherapy only or chemoradiotherapy)

and M stage are also included with each case although some variables are not available for all patients.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The total number of cases should be more than 1500 from at least 15 centers (the GORTEC cohort is multicentric, and we should get datasets from at least 3 centers within it). The total number of training cases is approximately 850 from 9 different centers. No specific validation cases are provided, and the training set can be split in any manner for cross-validation. The test cases of the 2022 challenge will be moved to the 2023 training set. The total number of test cases should be approximately 700 from at least six centers, consisting of new and previously unseen cases (none are publicly available).

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

For this new edition, we include new data from at least six additional centers (a multicentric cohort GORTEC with several hundreds of patients from a dozen centers, from which we should be able to collect around 300 patients from at least 3 centers, CHUB, CHUN, and HUG). The training set will comprise public and non-public data, whereas the test set will only include non-public data. There will be a total of at least 15 centers providing data. The training set will contain more diversity in centers (9) than the test set (at least 6).

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

Training and test cohorts are representative of the distribution of the real-world population of patients accepted for initial staging of oropharyngeal cancer.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

HECKTOR 2025 will incorporate new, unpublished data through four entirely new cohorts joining the consortium. These include one multicentric cohort (GORTEC) and centers from France and Switzerland, contributing approximately 400 previously unseen cases that will constitute the test set. This new data represents roughly 27% of the total challenge database of over 1,500 patients, with the remaining ~850 cases from previous HECKTOR data serving as the training set.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Original annotations were performed differently depending on the centers.

The training sets CHUV, CHUS, HGJ, HMR: Contours defining the GTVp and GTVn were drawn by an expert radiation oncologist in a radiotherapy treatment planning system. 40% (80 cases) of the training radiotherapy contours were directly drawn on the CT of the PET/CT scan and thereafter used for treatment planning. The remaining 60% (121) of the training radiotherapy contours were drawn on a different CT scan dedicated to treatment planning and were then registered to the FDG-PET/CT scan reference frame using intensity-based free-form deformable registration with the software MIM (MIM Software Inc., Cleveland, OH). For the training cases, the original number of annotators is unknown.

The training set CHUV: For each patient in the test set, the GTVp and GTVn were manually drawn on each FDG-PET/CT by a single expert radiation oncologist. Note that the segmentation of lymph nodes was performed with a separate delineation; therefore, the delineation of the primary tumor is only available for all cases and is the only one exploited in the present challenge.

The training set CHUP: the metabolic volume of primary tumors was automatically determined with the PET segmentation algorithm Fuzzy Locally Adaptive Bayesian (FLAB) (Hatt et al. 2009) and was then edited and corrected manually by a single expert based on the CT image, for example, to correct cases where the PET-defined delineation included air or non-tumoral tissues in the corresponding CT.

The training set MDA: Contours available from radiotherapy planning were refined according to the guidelines mentioned below.

The training set USZ: The primary tumor was separately segmented in the CT and PET images. The CT segmentation was performed manually. In all cases, two radiation oncologists with more than 10 years of experience were involved in the process. Contours were later post-processed for the presence of metal artifacts to exclude non-tumor-related effects. If a certain tumor slice was affected by any artifacts, the entire tumor contour was erased from that slice. Tumors with more than 50% of volume unsuitable for the analysis were excluded from the study. The voxels outside the soft tissue Hounsfield unit (HU) range (20 HU to 180 HU) were discarded. The tumor in the PET image was auto-segmented using a gradient-based method implemented in MIMVISTA (MIM Software Inc., Cleveland, OH).

The training set CHB: For each patient, the GTVp and GTVn were manually drawn using PET VCAR (GE Healthcare) software on each FDG-PET/CT by senior nuclear medicine physicians using adaptive thresholding with visual control using merged PET and CT information.

New testing sets: annotators will follow the established guidelines of previous years (see below) for consistency.

IMPORTANT: In the previous editions of the HECKTOR challenge, quality controls were performed by a board of 4 experts (certified as both radiologist and/or nuclear medicine physician) on all the datasets (training and test) to ensure consistency in ground-truth contours definition. The experts re-annotated them, when necessary, to the real tumoral volume (often smaller than volumes delineated for radiotherapy). A shared cloud environment (MIM Cloud Software Inc.) was used to centralize the contouring task and homogenize annotation software. For cases without original GTVn contours for radiotherapy, the experts annotated the cases using PET/CT fusion and N staging information. The board of experts developed a guideline for this quality control and reported in the following. We will use a similar methodology in the 2025 edition to ensure homogeneity and quality of the contours for all centers.

Guidelines for primary tumor annotation in PET/CT images:

Oropharyngeal lesions are contoured on PET/CT using information from PET and unenhanced CT acquisitions. The contouring includes the entire edges of the morphologic anomaly as depicted on unenhanced CT (mainly

visualized as a mass effect) and the corresponding hypermetabolic volume, using PET acquisition, unenhanced CT, and PET/CT fusion visualizations based on automatic co-registration.

The contouring excludes the hypermetabolic activity projecting outside the physical limits of the lesion (for example, in the lumen of the airway or on the bony structures with no morphologic evidence of local invasion).

Standardized nomenclature per AAPM TG-263: GTVp

Special situations:

Check clinical nodal category to make sure you excluded nearby FDG-avid and/or enlarged lymph nodes (e.g., submandibular, high level II, and retropharyngeal)

In case of tonsillar fossa or base of tongue fullness/enlargement without corresponding FDG avidity, please review the clinical datasheet to rule out pre-radiation tonsillectomy or extensive biopsy. If so, this case should be excluded.

Guidelines for nodal metastase tumor annotation in PET/CT images:

Lymph nodes are contoured on PET/CT using information from PET and unenhanced CT acquisitions. The contouring includes the entire edges of the morphologic lymphadenopathy as depicted on unenhanced CT and the corresponding hypermetabolic volume, using PET acquisition, unenhanced CT, and PET/CT fusion visualizations based on automatic co-registration for all cervical lymph node levels. Standardized nomenclature for lymph node ROI: GTVn.

The contouring excludes the hypermetabolic activity projecting outside the physical limits of the lesion (for example, on the bordering bony, muscular, or vascular structures).

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The expert radiation oncologists annotated the images for radiotherapy treatment planning without specific instruction beyond the official contouring guidelines for radiotherapy planning. For quality control, the annotator (who is both a radiologist and a nuclear medicine physician) was instructed to refine the original annotation to focus on radiologically suspicious cancer regions. Two non-experts (organizers of the challenge) performed an initial cleaning to facilitate the expert's work. The expert either validated or edited the VOIs.

For the quality control phase in all centers, we will use the guidelines and centralized procedure detailed in 23a).

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The original annotators of the training and test cases were expert radiation oncologists with unknown expertise in terms of number of years of professional expertise. The annotator who performed the quality control is both an expert radiologist and nuclear medicine physician.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

A single annotation was performed, no merging was necessary.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The preprocessing involves (for both the training and test cases): (i) Computation of the Standardized Uptake Value (SUV) for the PET images (ii) Conversion of the DICOM file format to NIfTI format. The code is available on the GitHub repository: <https://github.com/voreille/hecktor>.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

We evaluated the inter-observer agreement of 4 annotators, including a radiologist(s), nuclear medicine physician(s), and a radiation oncologist(s), on a subset of 21 cases randomly drawn from the test and train data of HECKTOR 2020. The average DSC computed on the six pairs of annotators was 0.61. In the literature, (Gudi et al. 2017) reported similar agreement with an average inter-observer DSC of 57% and 69% on CT and PET/CT, respectively, for GTV segmentation (primary and lymph nodes). A source of error, therefore, originates from the degree of subjectivity in the expert's annotation and correction.

For most patients of the dataset of HECKTOR 2020, the tumors were contoured on another CT scan. The two CTs were registered (as described in 23a), and the annotations were transformed according to the registrations. Thus, the main error source came from the original annotation registration. The quality control that we ran largely reduced this source of error. Similar quality control will be performed on the new data to homogenize the data.

Another potential error source is the lack of CT images with a contrast agent for a more accurate delineation of the primary tumor.

We will plan a new inter-observer agreement study on a subset of cases.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if

any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

In 2022, we used the aggregated Dice. For 2025, we propose improving the evaluation by relying on the framework proposed by Carass et al. (Sci Rep 2020) to better account for the various possible overlaps and detection rates between the ground truth and the segmentation outputs in situations where the number of lesions is not known a priori, which is the case for our data.

We will compute the Dice (DSC) for the GTVp, and for GTVn, we will compute both the aggregated DSC (similar to HECKTOR 2022) and an aggregated F1-Score for detection as follows. We count and accumulate true positives (TPs), false negatives (FNs), and false positive (FPs) lesion detections on the entire test set in this way:

1-1: TP

0-1: FN

1-0: FP

1-N: 1 TP, N-1 FNs

M-1: 1 TP, M-1 FPs

M-N: min(M,N) TPs and FPs (M-N, if M>N) or FNs (N-M, if M<N)

Where a detection is for IoU>30%. Where 1-1, 0-1, 1-0, 1-N, M-1, and M-N correspond to the various overlap configurations listed in Figure 1 of the paper by Carass et al (Sci Rep 2020) below. Similarly to the aggregated DSC, the aggregated F1-score is then, for the entire test set:

$$F1_{agg} = 2TP / (2TP + FP + FN).$$

While the proposed framework by Carass et al. (Sci Rep) introduces a new approach, comparison with previous work remains partly possible. GTVp DSC is directly comparable to other studies, and GTVn DSC_{agg} aligns with prior HECKTOR editions. Prioritizing well-suited metrics over strict comparability ensures a more meaningful evaluation. In the overview paper, we can still report additional metrics—such as previous HECKTOR metrics (GTVp DSC_{agg}), GTVn DSC with strict FN handling, Average Precision for the top algorithm, and HD—but these may not be ideal for ranking.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The proposed metrics are based on the framework published in Carass et al. (Sci Rep 2020), which is well suited to evaluate this type of task. GTVn and GTVp rankings are not based on the same metrics because of a main difference between them and the clinical questions: we know the patients have a primary tumor, and we want to segment it, but we do not know if they have any metastatic nodes (and if they have, how many). We want to find them and segment them.

GTVp: Always (almost always) one GTVp volume per patient so the standard DSC can evaluate it.

GTVn: 0, 1 or more GTVn volumes per patient. The main problem is 0 volumes, which motivates TPs, FPs, and FNs aggregation across all test cases (at the voxel and lesion levels). We want to evaluate both the detection and segmentation of these GTVn volumes.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

We will obtain a rank on GTVp and another on GTVn and compute the Borda count of these two rankings.

The rankings are then defined as:

- (1) The GTVp ranking is based on the mean DSC across all patients.
- (2) The GTVn ranking is based on the Borda count of two rankings. (2.a) GTVn segmentation ranking: Aggregated DSC on GTVn, similar to HECKTOR 2022 (2.b) GTVn detection ranking: Aggregated F1-score on GTVn.

This comprehensive multi-metric approach for different tumor structures makes statistical ties extremely unlikely, as teams would need to achieve identical performance across multiple evaluation dimensions simultaneously. The complementary nature of these metrics ensures robust evaluation of both detection accuracy and segmentation quality.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

In the unlikely event of missing results on the test case, we will consider that the model predicted no GTVp nor GTVn. This imputed prediction will be used to compute the average metric.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The goal is to identify segmentation methods that perform well on the two types of GTV and can accurately both detect, differentiate and segment lesions.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

A paired Wilcoxon signed-rank test will be used on the average metric per patient to statistically compare algorithm results. The Python SciPy library will be used for the statistical analyses. For the multiple comparison

testing (comparison of one vs multiple groups), correction will be used (Bonferroni). This test is computed to assess a significant difference between the first-ranked algorithms and the following ones (2nd, 3rd, etc.).

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

We will use a paired test since we want to compare the performance of the algorithms for each patient individually. The paired Wilcoxon signed-rank allows us to perform the analysis with minimal hypotheses.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

Similarly to 2022, an ensemble using STAPLE (Warfield, Zou, and Wells 2004) will be performed with all the predictions from the participants, as well as only the five best.

The correlation of the performance with the tumor size will be evaluated. The results will be compared across the different centers of the test set. In addition, an analysis of the location of segmentation false positives will be used to reveal if they are located near the primary tumor or other regions of the oropharynx.

TASK 2: Recurrence-Free Survival (RFS) prediction

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Provide a fully automated prediction of the risk of recurrence (recurrence-free survival) based on the multimodal FDG PET/CT images, the available clinical information, and the radiotherapy planning dose maps associated with the dosimetry CT (using all or only parts of the available information at the participant's discretion). Evaluated based on the C-index, ranking from the lowest to the highest C-index, the highest value wins.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Head and Neck cancer, PET/CT, multimodal, outcome prediction

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

- Numan Saeed: Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- Muhammad Ridzuan: Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- Shahad Hardan: Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- Salma Hassan: Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- Darya Taratynova: Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- Ufaq Khan: Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- Umair Nawaz: Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- Yutong Xie: Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- Mohammad Yaqub: Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- Arman Rahmim: BC Cancer Research Institute, Vancouver, Canada
- Fereshteh Yousefirizi: BC Cancer Research Institute, Vancouver, Canada
- Adrien Depeursinge: Institute of Information Systems, University of Applied Sciences Western Switzerland (HES-SO), Sierre, Switzerland and CHUV
- Vincent Andrearczyk: Institute of Information Systems, University of Applied Sciences Western Switzerland (HES-SO), Sierre, Switzerland
- Mathieu Hatt: LaTIM, INSERM, UMR 1101, Univ Brest, Brest, France
- Isaac Shiri: Bern University Hospital

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

- Muhammad Ridzuan: muhammad.ridzuan@mbzuai.ac.ae
- Salma Hassan: salma.hassan@mbzuai.ac.ae
- Mathieu Hatt: mathieu.hatt@inserm.fr

- Ufaq Khan: ufaq.khan@mbzuai.ac.ae

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

Challenge associated with MICCAI 2025

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

2025 will be updated later on grand-challenge (2022 website: <https://hecktor.grand-challenge.org/>)

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Participants may use additional public data to extend the provided dataset for training the algorithm chosen for ranking, but the use of private data (e.g., from their own institutions) is strictly prohibited. Similarly, models pretrained on private datasets are not permitted. This policy ensures a fair comparison among all participating methods. However, participants may use both public and private data for scientific publication purposes, provided they explicitly disclose this in their submitted manuscripts and include results obtained using only the provided HECKTOR2025 data to highlight any potential differences.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

Award for the best-ranked team, conditioned on a paper submission reporting the details of the methods. In the event that teams achieve identical metric scores or statistical analysis reveals no significant performance differences between top-ranking teams, we will equitably divide the awards among those teams. This approach ensures fairness while preserving the competitive spirit of the challenge and recognizes equivalent technical achievements.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

The results and winner will be announced publicly.

Once participants submit their results on the test set to the challenge organizers via the challenge website, they will be considered fully vested in the challenge, so that their performance results (without identifying the participant unless permission is granted) will become part of any presentations, publications, or subsequent analyses derived from the Challenge at the discretion of the organizers.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

The participating teams are encouraged to publish their results in the LNCS proceedings of the challenge (following the MICCAI proceedings timeline and subject to acceptance). Participants can submit their results elsewhere when citing the overview paper, and (if so) no embargo will be applied.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

The participating teams will submit the prediction outputs via grand-challenge.org. We will provide a link to the submission instructions.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

The task submission is divided into 1+2 phases: sanity check, validation (Phase 1), and testing (Phase 2).

The sanity check consists of 3 images. Its purpose is to ensure that the participating teams are familiar with the Grand Challenge platform and that their dockers run without errors. All teams will make their submission to the

sanity check phase and will receive feedback on their errors.

The validation phase (Phase 1) consists of about 50 images. All teams will submit 2 working dockers from the sanity check to the validation phase. Only the top 15 teams, as ranked by the evaluation metric and displayed on the public validation leaderboard, with valid submissions will proceed to Phase 2.

The testing phase (Phase 2) consists of about 400 images. The teams will choose 1 of 2 dockers from the validation phase to be submitted to the testing phase. The official ranking of the teams will be based on the testing phase. We will request that each run must be specifically identified and described in the team report accompanying the submissions.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

- 1) Release of the Training Cases: 15th May 2025
- 2) Validation Submission: 10th July to 10th August 2025
- 3) Selection & Announcement of the Top 15 Teams: 10th August to 14th August 2025
- 4) Testing Submission: opens 15th August 2025, closes 1st September 2025
- 5) Final Report Submission: 8th September 2025
- 6) Announcement of the Top 5 Teams: 15th September 2025
- 7) Associated Workshop Days: Either 23rd or 27th September 2025

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

We indicate the answers for the cases of the different centers.

- Montreal, CA: CHUM, CHUS, HGJ, HMR (train): The ethics approval was granted by the Research Ethics Committee of McGill University Health Center (Protocol Number: MM-JGH-CR15-50).
- Lausanne, CH: CHUV (train): The ethics approval was obtained from the Commission cantonale (VD) d'éthique de la recherche sur l'être humain (CER-VD) with protocol number: 2018-01513.
- Poitiers, FR: CHUP (train): The fully anonymized data originates from patients who consent to use their data for research purposes.
- Houston: MDA (train): The ethics approval was obtained from the University of Texas MD Anderson Cancer Center Institutional Review Board with protocol number RCR03-0800.

- Zürich, CH, USZ (train): The ethics approval was related to the clinical trial NCT01435252 entitled "A Phase II Study In Patients With Advanced Head And Neck Cancer Of Standard Chemoradiation And Add-On Cetuximab."
- Rouen, FR: CHB (train): The fully anonymized data originates from patients who consent to use their data for research purposes.
- Brest, FR: CHUB (test): The fully anonymized data originates from patients who consent to use their data for research purposes.
- Nantes, FR: CHUN (test): The fully anonymized data originates from patients who consent to use their data for research purposes.
- GORTEC (test): The fully anonymized data originates from patients who consent to use their data for research purposes.
- Geneve, CH: HUG (test): The fully anonymized data originates from patients who consent to use their data for research purposes.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The code to produce the results and ranking will be made available on our GitHub repository. Link to the full code and documentation will be added to the challenge page.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Although the participating teams will be strongly encouraged to disclose or share their code, it will remain optional.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The challenge is funded by the BioMedIA Lab at the Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, and partly funded by Society of Nuclear Medicine and Molecular Imaging (SNMMI) AI task force. Companies who funded HECKTOR 2021 and 2022 such as Aquilab, and Bioemtech will be contacted to sponsor the challenge. Additional companies will also be contacted to secure funding.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

The participating algorithms target automated prediction of outcome.

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation

- Tracking

Prediction, Modeling

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Same as Task 1. The clinical goal is the stratification of the population for personalized patient management.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Patients with histologically proven oropharyngeal H&N; cancer who underwent (chemo)radiotherapy treatment with curative intent.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

FDG-PET/CT scans (both functional FDG PET and low-dose CT modalities acquired with the same multimodal scanner are considered), with the addition of dosemaps from the radiotherapy planning along with the associated dosimetry CT (used for calculating the dose).

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The information on image data will include clinical center, scanner information, DICOM meta-data including acquisition parameters and reconstruction algorithms, with the addition of meta-data information for the dosimetry CT and dosemaps.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

The patient information will include center, age, gender, tobacco and alcohol consumption, performance status, treatment (radiotherapy only or chemoradiotherapy, and M stage (T and N stage will not be provided as it informs on lymph nodes status which is part of the goal of Task 1). HPV status will be provided for the training set but not the testing set (since it will be the ground-truth of Task 3). There are missing values for some patients, although an effort will be carried out by each clinical center to update the information as much as possible.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The data originates from FDG-PET and low-dose non-contrast-enhanced CT images (acquired with combined PET/CT scanners) of the H&N region. In addition, dosimetry CT and dosemaps of the same region.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Same as Task 1, except information in the image (as well as clinical factors) from outside the GTVp and GTVn might also be exploited.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The device(s) used to acquire the training and testing images are listed in the following for the different centers .

- HGJ: A hybrid PET/CT GE Discovery ST
- CHUS: A hybrid PET/CT PhilipsGXL 16.
- HMR: A hybrid PET/CT GE Discovery STE
- CHUM: A hybrid PET/CT GE Discovery STE
- CHUV: A hybrid PET/CT GE Discovery D690 TOF
- CHUP: A hybrid PET/CT Siemens Biograph mCT 40 ToF.
- MDA: Multiple hybrid PET/CT GE devices: Discovery HR, Discovery RX, Discovery ST, Discovery STE
- USZ: Multiple hybrid PET/CT GE devices: Discovery HR, Discovery RX, Discovery STE, Discovery LS, Discovery 690
- CHB: A hybrid PET/CT GE710.
- CHUN: A hybrid PET/CT Siemens mCT 64 vision
- CHUB: Multiple hybrid PET/CT scanner devices: Philips GEMINI, Siemens Biograph, Siemens Biograph Vision
- HUG: A hybrid PET/CT Siemens Biograph 64 True Point scanner
- GORTEC: Multiple hybrid PET/CT scanner devices

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

1) HGJ:

For the PET portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median of 584 MBq (range: 368-715) was injected intravenously. After a 90-minute uptake period of rest, patients were imaged with the PET/CT imaging system. Imaging acquisition of the head and neck was performed using multiple bed positions with a median of 300 s (range: 180-420) per bed position. Attenuation-corrected images were reconstructed using an ordered subset expectation maximization (OSEM) iterative algorithm and a span (axial mash) of 5. The FDG-PET slice thickness resolution was 3.27 mm for all patients, and the median in-plane resolution was 3.52×3.52 mm² (range: 3.52-4.69). For the CT portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, an energy of 140 kVp with an exposure of 12 mAs was used. The CT slice thickness resolution was 3.75 mm, and the median in-plane resolution was 0.98×0.98 mm² for all patients.

2) CHUS:

For the PET portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median of 325 MBq (range: 165-517) was injected intravenously. After a 90-minute uptake period of rest, patients were imaged with the PET/CT imaging system. Imaging acquisition of the head and neck was performed using multiple bed positions with a median of 150 s (range: 120-151) per bed position. Attenuation-corrected images were reconstructed using a LOR-RAMLA iterative algorithm. The FDG-PET slice thickness resolution was 4 mm, and the median in-plane resolution was 4×4 mm² for all patients. For the CT portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median energy of 140 kVp (range: 12-140) with a median exposure of 210 mAs (range: 43-250) was used. The median CT slice thickness resolution was 3 mm (range: 2-5,) and the median in-plane resolution was 1.17×1.17 mm² (range: 0.68-1.17).

3) HMR:

For the PET portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median of 475 MBq (range: 227-859) was injected intravenously. After a 90-minute uptake period of rest, patients were imaged with the PET/CT imaging system. Imaging acquisition of the head and neck was performed using multiple bed positions with a median of 360 s (range: 120-360) per bed position. Attenuation-corrected images were reconstructed using an ordered subset expectation maximization (OSEM) iterative algorithm and a median span (axial mash) of 5 (range: 3-5). The FDG-PET slice thickness resolution was 3.27 mm for all patients, and the median in-plane resolution was 3.52×3.52 mm² (range: 3.52-5.47). For the CT portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median energy of 140 kVp (range: 120-140) with a median exposure of 11 mAs (range: 5-16) was used. The CT slice thickness resolution was 3.75 mm for all patients, and the median in-plane resolution was 0.98×0.98 mm² (range: 0.98-1.37).

4) CHUM:

For the PET portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median of 315 MBq (range: 199-3182) was injected intravenously. After a 90-minute uptake period of rest, patients were imaged with the PET/CT imaging system. Imaging acquisition of the head and neck was performed using multiple bed positions with a median of 300 s (range: 120-420) per bed position. Attenuation-corrected images were reconstructed using an ordered subset expectation maximization (OSEM) iterative algorithm and a median span (axial mash) of 3 (range: 3-5). The median FDG-PET slice thickness resolution was 4 mm (range: 3.27-4), and the median in-plane resolution was 4×4 mm² (range: 3.52-5.47). For the CT portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median energy of 120 kVp (range: 120-140) with a median exposure of 350 mAs (range: 5-350) was used. The median CT slice thickness resolution was 1.5 mm (range: 1.5-3.75,) and the median in-plane resolution was 0.98×0.98 mm² (range: 0.98-1.37).

5) CHUV:

The patients fasted at least 4 hours before the injection of 4 Mbq/kg of (18F)-FDG (Flucis). Blood glucose levels were checked before injecting (18F)-FDG. If not contra-indicated, intravenous contrast agents were administered before CT scanning. After a 60-minute uptake period of rest, patients were imaged with the PET/CT imaging system. First, a CT (120 kV, 80 mA, 0.8-s rotation time, slice thickness 3.75 mm) was performed from the base of the skull to the mid-thigh. PET scanning was performed immediately after the acquisition of the CT. Images were acquired from the base of the skull to the mid-thigh (3 min/bed position). PET images were reconstructed by using an ordered-subset expectation maximization iterative reconstruction (OSEM) (two iterations, 28 subsets) and an iterative fully 3D (DiscoveryST). CT data were used for attenuation calculation.

6) CHUP:

PET/CT acquisition began after 6 hours of fasting and 60 ± 5 min after injection of 3 MBq/kg of 18F-FDG (421 ± 98 MBq, range 220-695 MBq). Non-contrast-enhanced, non-respiratory gated (free breathing) CT images were acquired for attenuation correction (120 kVp, Care Dose® current modulation system) with an in-plane resolution of 0.853×0.853 mm² and a 5 mm slice thickness. PET data were acquired using 2.5 minutes per bed position routine protocol, and images were reconstructed using a CT-based attenuation correction and the OSEM-TrueX-TOF algorithm (with time-of-flight and spatial resolution modeling, 3 iterations and 21 subsets, 5 mm 3D Gaussian post-filtering, voxel size $4 \times 4 \times 4$ mm³).

7) MDA:

For the PET portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median of 401 MBq (range: 327-266) was injected intravenously. After a 90-minute uptake period of rest, patients were imaged with the PET/CT imaging system. Image acquisition of the head and neck was performed using multiple bed positions with a median of 180 s (range: 90-300) per bed position. Attenuation-corrected images were reconstructed using an ordered subset expectation maximization (OSEM) iterative algorithm (2 iterations, 18-24 subsets, 5mm Gaussian filter). The median FDG-PET slice thickness was 3.27 mm (range: 2.99-5), and the median in-plane resolution was 5.46×5.46 mm² (range: 2.73×2.73 - 5.46×5.46). For the CT portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median energy of 120 kVp (range: 100-140) with a median exposure of 185 mAs (range: 10-397) was used. The median CT slice thickness resolution was 3.75mm (range: 2.99-5), and the median in-plane resolution was 0.98×0.98 mm² (range: 0.48×0.48 - 2.734×2.734).

8) USZ:

For PET imaging, an activity of 178–513 MBq was administered intravenously 1h prior to the scan and after measuring blood sugar level. In the retrospective cohort, 2D or 3D iterative image reconstruction was used, whereas the images of the validation cohort were reconstructed with a 3D algorithm.

9) CHB:

Head and neck PET-CT images were acquired on a GE710 PET-CT device (General Electric, Milwaukee, USA) 90 minutes (± 5 min) after injecting approximately 3 MBq/kg of FDG. PET and CT acquisition parameters were adapted to the patient's habitus with the patient in the radiotherapy treatment position with a contention mask. For the unenhanced CT portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, an energy of 120 kVp with an exposure of 25 mAs was used. Attenuation-corrected images were reconstructed using an ordered subset expectation maximization (OSEM) iterative algorithm (VPFX, 2 iterations, and 23 subsets) and a span (axial mash) of 5. The FDG-PET slice thickness resolution was 3.27 mm for all patients, and the median in-plane resolution was 2.73×2.73 mm². The CT slice thickness resolution was 2.5 mm, and the median in-plane resolution was 0.98×0.98 mm² for all patients.

10) CHUN:

After 6h fasting; 3MBq/kg; Acquisition 60 min post-injection; contrast agent if possible, acquisition steps adapted to patient's morphology

Siemens Biograph mCT: Data were reconstructed using the 3D ordinary Poisson ordered subset expectation maximization algorithm with point spread function recovery and time-of-flight information. The reconstruction parameters were 3 iterations, 21 subsets with a 2-mm full width at half maximum (FWHM) Gaussian post-filtering (voxel size $4 \times 4 \times 2$ mm³). Low-dose CT 3D was acquired for attenuation and scatter correction, with or without intravenous contrast enhancement, and automatic mA according to the patient's weight.

Siemens Biograph Vision 450: Data were reconstructed using the 3D ordinary Poisson ordered subset expectation maximization algorithm with point spread function recovery and time-of-flight information. The reconstruction parameters were 4 iterations and 5 subsets with a 3-mm FWHM Gaussian post-filtering for the Biograph Vision 450 (voxel size $1.65 \times 1.65 \times 1.65$ mm³). Low-dose CT 3D was acquired for attenuation and scatter correction, with or without intravenous contrast enhancement, and automatic mA according to the patient's weight.

11) HUG:

After fasting for 6h, all patients had a single [18F]FDG injection, followed by a PET/MRI and a subsequent PET/CT scan. A mean dose of 373 ± 28 MBq [18F]FDG was injected intravenously into all patients before the PET/MRI examination was started. During the time necessary for radiotracer uptake, a dedicated MRI of the HN region (T2-weighted, diffusion-weighted, and T1-weighted sequences before and after iv. administration of a gadolinium-based contrast material), followed by total body MRI sequences was performed. The total body MRI sequences (see below) were used for attenuation correction, lesion detection, anatomic localization, and lesion characterization. Afterward, a whole-body PET was acquired on the PET/MRI system. The patient was then transferred to the PET/CT scanner, and no additional [18F]FDG was injected. PET/CT images were acquired on a Biograph 64 True Point scanner (Siemens Healthcare, Erlangen, Germany). The standard dose CT scan used for attenuation correction and diagnosis (with soft tissue, bone, and lung windows) had the following parameters: 120kVp, 180mAs, pitch = 1.2, collimation = 24×1.5 , 1 s per rotation, reconstructed CT slice thickness = 2 mm, reconstruction interval = 1.5 mm. PET data acquisition was started 120 ± 21 min after injection of [18F]FDG with a total of 8–9 bed positions. The delay between the end of the PET acquisition on the PET/MRI machine and the start of the PET acquisition on the PET/CT machine was, on average, 26 min. No iodine-based iv. contrast material was administered because: (1) according to the ESUR guidelines, for patients with a normal or moderately reduced GFR, there should be ≥ 4 h between injections of gadolinium- and iodine-based contrast agents [25]; (2) current guidelines for PET/CT do not recommend the routine use of iv. iodine-based contrast in all PET/CT examinations. The AWOSEM iterative reconstruction algorithm (4 iterations, 8 subsets, voxel size = $4 \times 4 \times 5$ mm³) was applied for PET reconstruction. Standardized uptake values (SUVs) were calculated separately for PET/MRI and PET/CT according to the standard formula.

12) CHUB: Details to collect (standard clinical protocol)

13) GORTEC: Details to collect (standard clinical protocol)

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

These are the list of centers that are confirmed:

- HGJ: Hôpital général juif, Montréal, CA
- CHUS: Centre hospitalier universitaire de Sherbrooke, Sherbrooke, CA
- HMR: Hôpital Maisonneuve-Rosemont, Montréal, CA
- CHUM: Centre hospitalier de l'Université de Montréal, Montréal, CA
- CHUV: Centre Hospitalier Universitaire Vaudois, CH
- CHUP: Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Poitiers, FR
- CHUN: Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Nantes, FR
- HUG: Hôpitaux Universitaires de Genève, CH
- GORTEC: Multiple French/Swiss centers, details currently being collected

These centers were included in the 2022 edition and have shown interest in joining the 2025 challenge, but we are waiting for the final approvals:

- MDA: MD Anderson Cancer Center, Houston, Texas, USA
- CHB: Centre Henri Becquerel, Rouen, FR
- USZ: UniversitätsSpital Zürich, CH
- CHUB: Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Brest, FR

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

None.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Training and testing cases represent one 3D FDG-PET volume registered with a 3D CT volume of the head and neck region, as well as contours with the annotated ground truth lesions (only available for training cases to the participating teams). The labels will have three values: background with the value 0, primary Gross Tumor Volumes (GTVp) with the value 1, and nodal Gros Tumor Volumes (GTVn) with the value 2 (in case of several lymph nodes, they are considered all with the same label). Patient information including center, age, gender, tobacco and alcohol consumption, performance status, HPV status, treatment (radiotherapy only or chemoradiotherapy) and M stage are also included with each case although some variables are not available for all patients. In

addition, the cases also include the patient outcome information (only available for training cases to the participating teams) of recurrence-free survival (time-to-event in days and censoring), as well as the dosimetry CT and the corresponding radiotherapy dose map for some of the patients.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The total number of cases should be more than 1500 from at least 15 centers (the GORTEC cohort is multicentric, and we should get datasets from at least 3 centers within it). The total number of training cases is approximately 850 from 9 different centers. No specific validation cases are provided, and the training set can be split in any manner for cross-validation. The test cases of the 2022 challenge will be moved to the 2023 training set. The total number of test cases should be approximately 700 from at least six centers, consisting of new and previously unseen cases (none are publicly available).

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

For this new edition, we include new data from at least six additional centers (a multicentric cohort GORTEC with several hundreds of patients from a dozen centers, from which we should be able to collect around 300 patients from at least 3 centers, CHUB, CHUN, and HUG). The training set will comprise public and non-public data, whereas the test set will only include non-public data. There will be a total of at least 15 centers providing data. The training set will contain more diversity in centers (9) than the test set (at least 6). If we cannot complete the quality control of GTv_p and GTv_n ROIs for all cases for Task 1, the entire cohort could still be used for Task 2 as the contours are not provided to the participants in this case. Participants can elect to segment the volumes for characterization or use other approaches not requiring segmentation.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

Training and test cohorts are representative of the distribution of the real-world population of patients accepted for initial staging of oropharyngeal cancer.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

HECKTOR 2025 will incorporate new, unpublished data through four entirely new cohorts joining the consortium. These include one multicentric cohort (GORTEC) and centers from France and Switzerland, contributing approximately 400 previously unseen cases that will constitute the test set. This new data represents roughly 27% of the total challenge database of over 1,500 patients, with the remaining ~850 cases from previous HECKTOR data serving as the training set.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The outcome ground truths for the prediction task were collected in patients' records as registered by clinicians during patient follow-ups. These include locoregional failures and distant metastases. The time t=0 is fixed to the PET/CT scan date for all centers.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

No specific instructions. The patients' outcomes were collected and recorded in the patient's records at the last follow-up.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Not applicable.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Not applicable.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Same as Task 1 for the images. No preprocessing of the patient outcomes is required.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

A source of error inherent to the task of survival analysis is the censored data (e.g., due to death or cessation of follow-up).

The median follow-up period is approximately 40 months (5-110 months) on the training set.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Concordance index (C-index).

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The concordance index (C-index) quantifies the model's ability to accurately rank the survival times based on the computed individual risk scores, generalizing the area under the ROC curve (AUC). It can account for censored data and represents the global assessment of the model discrimination power (Uno et al. 2011).

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

The ranking will be based on the C-index value obtained in the test cohort. The participant with the highest C-index wins.

A bootstrap will be performed on the test set to evaluate the variance of the C-index of each team and for statistical comparison of algorithms results. This bootstrap approach provides confidence intervals for each team's performance, allowing us to determine whether differences between top-performing teams are statistically significant.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

In the unlikely event of a missing score for one patient, all the pairs containing the missing score will be treated as non-concordant.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The C-index is a widely used survival analysis metric that considers time-to-event information and censored data. (Harrell 1982) (Uno et al. 2011)

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

A bootstrap will be performed on the test set to evaluate the variance of the C-index of each team and for statistical comparison of algorithm results. The Python SciPy and Scikit-learn libraries will be used for the statistical analyses.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The bootstrap analysis allows us to simulate different sampling of the test set to approximate the variance of the C-index.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

A consensus of the best models will be evaluated using the C-index to establish whether there is complementary value for prognosis. Similarly to Task 1, we will compare the results obtained on the different centers of the test set.

TASK 3: Diagnosis of HPV status

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Provide a fully automated diagnosis of the HPV status (positive or negative) based on the multimodal FDG PET/CT images and the available clinical information (using all or only parts of the available information at the participant's discretion). Evaluated based on the balanced accuracy (BAcc), ranking from the lowest to the highest BAcc, the highest value wins. In the case of ties, the highest specificity wins.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Head and Neck cancer, PET/CT, multimodal, diagnosis

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

- Numan Saeed: Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- Muhammad Ridzuan: Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- Shahad Hardan: Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- Salma Hassan: Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- Darya Taratynova: Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- Ufaq Khan: Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- Umair Nawaz: Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- Yutong Xie: Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- Mohammad Yaqub: Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- Arman Rahmim: BC Cancer Research Institute, Vancouver, Canada
- Fereshteh Yousefirizi: BC Cancer Research Institute, Vancouver, Canada
- Adrien Depeursinge: Institute of Information Systems, University of Applied Sciences Western Switzerland (HES-SO), Sierre, Switzerland and CHUV
- Vincent Andrearczyk: Institute of Information Systems, University of Applied Sciences Western Switzerland (HES-SO), Sierre, Switzerland
- Mathieu Hatt: LaTIM, INSERM, UMR 1101, Univ Brest, Brest, France
- Isaac Shiri: Bern University Hospital

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

- Shahad Hardan: shahad.hardan@mbzuai.ac.ae
- Darya Taratynova: darya.taratynova@mbzuai.ac.ae
- Mathieu Hatt: mathieu.hatt@inserm.fr

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

Challenge associated with MICCAI 2025

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

2025 will be updated later on grand-challenge (2022 website: <https://hecktor.grand-challenge.org/>)

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Participants may use additional public data to extend the provided dataset for training the algorithm chosen for ranking, but the use of private data (e.g., from their own institutions) is strictly prohibited. Similarly, models pretrained on private datasets are not permitted. This policy ensures a fair comparison among all participating methods. However, participants may use both public and private data for scientific publication purposes, provided they explicitly disclose this in their submitted manuscripts and include results obtained using only the provided HECKTOR2025 data to highlight any potential differences.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

Award for the best-ranked team, conditioned on a paper submission reporting the details of the methods. In the event that teams achieve identical metric scores or statistical analysis reveals no significant performance differences between top-ranking teams, we will equitably divide the awards among those teams. This approach

ensures fairness while preserving the competitive spirit of the challenge and recognizes equivalent technical achievements.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

The results and winner will be announced publicly.

Once participants submit their results on the test set to the challenge organizers via the challenge website, they will be considered fully vested in the challenge, so that their performance results (without identifying the participant unless permission is granted) will become part of any presentations, publications, or subsequent analyses derived from the Challenge at the discretion of the organizers.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

The participating teams are encouraged to publish their results in the LNCS proceedings of the challenge (following the MICCAI proceedings timeline and subject to acceptance). Participants can submit their results elsewhere when citing the overview paper, and (if so) no embargo will be applied.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

The participating teams will submit diagnostic outputs via grand-challenge.org. We will provide a link to the submission instructions.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

The task submission is divided into 1+2 phases: sanity check, validation (Phase 1), and testing (Phase 2).

The sanity check consists of 3 images. Its purpose is to ensure that the participating teams are familiar with the Grand Challenge platform and that their dockers run without errors. All teams will make their submission to the sanity check phase and will receive feedback on their errors.

The validation phase (Phase 1) consists of about 50 images. All teams will submit 2 working dockers from the

sanity check to the validation phase. Only the top 15 teams, as ranked by the evaluation metric and displayed on the public validation leaderboard, with valid submissions will proceed to Phase 2.

The testing phase (Phase 2) consists of about 400 images. The teams will choose 1 of 2 dockers from the validation phase to be submitted to the testing phase. The official ranking of the teams will be based on the testing phase. We will request that each run must be specifically identified and described in the team report accompanying the submissions.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

- 1) Release of the Training Cases: 15th May 2025
- 2) Validation Submission: 10th July to 10th August 2025
- 3) Selection & Announcement of the Top 15 Teams: 10th August to 14th August 2025
- 4) Testing Submission: opens 15th August 2025, closes 1st September 2025
- 5) Final Report Submission: 8th September 2025
- 6) Announcement of the Top 5 Teams: 15th September 2025
- 7) Associated Workshop Days: Either 23rd or 27th September 2025

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

We indicate the answers for the cases of the different centers.

- Montreal, CA: CHUM, CHUS, HGJ, HMR (train): The ethics approval was granted by the Research Ethics Committee of McGill University Health Center (Protocol Number: MM-JGH-CR15-50).
- Lausanne, CH: CHUV (train): The ethics approval was obtained from the Commission cantonale (VD) d'éthique de la recherche sur l'être humain (CER-VD) with protocol number: 2018-01513.
- Poitiers, FR: CHUP (train): The fully anonymized data originates from patients who consent to use their data for research purposes.
- Houston: MDA (train): The ethics approval was obtained from the University of Texas MD Anderson Cancer Center Institutional Review Board with protocol number RCR03-0800.
- Zürich, CH, USZ (train): The ethics approval was related to the clinical trial NCT01435252 entitled "A Phase II Study In Patients With Advanced Head And Neck Cancer Of Standard Chemoradiation And Add-On Cetuximab."
- Rouen, FR: CHB (train): The fully anonymized data originates from patients who consent to use their data for

research purposes.

- Brest, FR: CHUB (test): The fully anonymized data originates from patients who consent to use their data for research purposes.
- Nantes, FR: CHUN (test): The fully anonymized data originates from patients who consent to use their data for research purposes.
- GORTEC (test): The fully anonymized data originates from patients who consent to use their data for research purposes.
- Geneve, CH: HUG (test): The fully anonymized data originates from patients who consent to use their data for research purposes.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The code to produce the results and ranking will be made available on our GitHub repository. Link to the full code and documentation will be added to the challenge page.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Although the participating teams will be strongly encouraged to disclose or share their code, it will remain optional.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The challenge is funded by the BioMedIA Lab at the Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, and partly funded by Society of Nuclear Medicine and Molecular Imaging (SNMMI) AI task force. Companies who funded HECKTOR 2021 and 2022 such as Aquilab, and Bioemtech will be contacted to sponsor the challenge. Additional companies will also be contacted to secure funding.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

The participating algorithms target automated diagnosis (HPV status).

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Diagnosis ,Modeling

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Same as Task 2. The clinical goal can also be considered as a digital biopsy approach, i.e. diagnosis based on the images, avoiding the actual invasive biopsy.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Patients with histologically proven oropharyngeal H&N; cancer who underwent (chemo)radiotherapy treatment with curative intent.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

FDG-PET/CT scans (both functional FDG PET and low-dose CT modalities acquired with the same multimodal scanner are considered).

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The information on image data will include clinical center, scanner information, DICOM meta-data including acquisition parameters and reconstruction algorithms.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

The patient information will include center, age, gender, tobacco and alcohol consumption, performance status, treatment (radiotherapy only or chemoradiotherapy, and M stage (T and N stage will not be provided as it informs on lymph nodes status which is part of the goal of Task 1). HPV status will be provided for the training set but not the testing set (since it will be the ground-truth of Task 3). There are missing values for some patients, although an effort will be carried out by each clinical center to update the information as much as possible.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The data originates from FDG-PET and low-dose non-contrast-enhanced CT images (acquired with combined PET/CT scanners) of the H&N; region.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm target is the H&N; oropharyngeal cancer primary Gross Tumor Volume (GTVp) and lymph node gross tumor volume (GTVn) lesions.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Sensitivity

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The device(s) used to acquire the training and testing images are listed in the following for the different centers .

- HGJ: A hybrid PET/CT GE Discovery ST
- CHUS: A hybrid PET/CT PhilipsGXL 16.
- HMR: A hybrid PET/CT GE Discovery STE
- CHUM: A hybrid PET/CT GE Discovery STE
- CHUV: A hybrid PET/CT GE Discovery D690 TOF
- CHUP: A hybrid PET/CT Siemens Biograph mCT 40 ToF.
- MDA: Multiple hybrid PET/CT GE devices: Discovery HR, Discovery RX, Discovery ST, Discovery STE
- USZ: Multiple hybrid PET/CT GE devices: Discovery HR, Discovery RX, Discovery STE, Discovery LS, Discovery 690
- CHB: A hybrid PET/CT GE710.
- CHUN: A hybrid PET/CT Siemens mCT 64 vision
- CHUB: Multiple hybrid PET/CT scanner devices: Philips GEMINI, Siemens Biograph, Siemens Biograph Vision
- HUG: A hybrid PET/CT Siemens Biograph 64 True Point scanner
- GORTEC: Multiple hybrid PET/CT scanner devices
- HGJ: A hybrid PET/CT GE Discovery ST
- CHUS: A hybrid PET/CT PhilipsGXL 16.
- HMR: A hybrid PET/CT GE Discovery STE
- CHUM: A hybrid PET/CT GE Discovery STE
- CHUV: A hybrid PET/CT GE Discovery D690 TOF
- CHUP: A hybrid PET/CT Siemens Biograph mCT 40 ToF.
- MDA: Multiple hybrid PET/CT GE devices: Discovery HR, Discovery RX, Discovery ST, Discovery STE
- USZ: Multiple hybrid PET/CT GE devices: Discovery HR, Discovery RX, Discovery STE, Discovery LS, Discovery

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- CHB: A hybrid PET/CT GE710.
- CHUN: A hybrid PET/CT Siemens mCT 64 vision
- CHUB: Multiple hybrid PET/CT scanner devices: Philips GEMINI, Siemens Biograph, Siemens Biograph Vision
- HUG: A hybrid PET/CT Siemens Biograph 64 True Point scanner
- GORTEC: Multiple hybrid PET/CT scanner devices

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

1) HGJ:

For the PET portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median of 584 MBq (range: 368-715) was injected intravenously. After a 90-minute uptake period of rest, patients were imaged with the PET/CT imaging system. Imaging acquisition of the head and neck was performed using multiple bed positions with a median of 300 s (range: 180-420) per bed position. Attenuation-corrected images were reconstructed using an ordered subset expectation maximization (OSEM) iterative algorithm and a span (axial mash) of 5. The FDG-PET slice thickness resolution was 3.27 mm for all patients, and the median in-plane resolution was $3.52 \times 3.52 \text{ mm}^2$ (range: 3.52-4.69). For the CT portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, an energy of 140 kVp with an exposure of 12 mAs was used. The CT slice thickness resolution was 3.75 mm, and the median in-plane resolution was $0.98 \times 0.98 \text{ mm}^2$ for all patients.

2) CHUS:

For the PET portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median of 325 MBq (range: 165-517) was injected intravenously. After a 90-minute uptake period of rest, patients were imaged with the PET/CT imaging system. Imaging acquisition of the head and neck was performed using multiple bed positions with a median of 150 s (range: 120-151) per bed position. Attenuation-corrected images were reconstructed using a LOR-RAMLA iterative algorithm. The FDG-PET slice thickness resolution was 4 mm, and the median in-plane resolution was $4 \times 4 \text{ mm}^2$ for all patients. For the CT portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median energy of 140 kVp (range: 12-140) with a median exposure of 210 mAs (range: 43-250) was used. The median CT slice thickness resolution was 3 mm (range: 2-5,) and the median in-plane resolution was $1.17 \times 1.17 \text{ mm}^2$ (range: 0.68-1.17).

3) HMR:

For the PET portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median of 475 MBq (range: 227-859) was injected intravenously. After a 90-minute uptake period of rest, patients were imaged with the PET/CT imaging system. Imaging acquisition of the head and neck was performed using multiple bed positions with a median of 360 s (range: 120-360) per bed position. Attenuation-corrected images were reconstructed using an ordered subset expectation maximization (OSEM) iterative algorithm and a median span (axial mash) of 5 (range: 3-5). The FDG-PET slice thickness resolution was 3.27 mm for all patients, and the median in-plane resolution was $3.52 \times 3.52 \text{ mm}^2$ (range: 3.52-5.47). For the CT portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median energy of 140 kVp (range: 120-140) with a median exposure of 11 mAs (range: 5-16) was used. The CT slice thickness resolution was 3.75 mm for all patients, and the median in-plane resolution was $0.98 \times 0.98 \text{ mm}^2$ (range: 0.98-1.37).

4) CHUM:

For the PET portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median of 315 MBq (range: 199-3182) was injected intravenously. After a 90-minute uptake period of rest, patients were imaged with the PET/CT imaging system. Imaging

acquisition of the head and neck was performed using multiple bed positions with a median of 300 s (range: 120-420) per bed position. Attenuation-corrected images were reconstructed using an ordered subset expectation maximization (OSEM) iterative algorithm and a median span (axial mash) of 3 (range: 3-5). The median FDG-PET slice thickness resolution was 4 mm (range: 3.27-4), and the median in-plane resolution was $4 \times 4 \text{ mm}^2$ (range: 3.52-5.47). For the CT portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median energy of 120 kVp (range: 120-140) with a median exposure of 350 mAs (range: 5-350) was used. The median CT slice thickness resolution was 1.5 mm (range: 1.5-3.75,) and the median in-plane resolution was $0.98 \times 0.98 \text{ mm}^2$ (range: 0.98-1.37).

5) CHUV:

The patients fasted at least 4 hours before the injection of 4 Mbq/kg of (18F)-FDG (Flucis). Blood glucose levels were checked before injecting (18F)-FDG. If not contra-indicated, intravenous contrast agents were administered before CT scanning. After a 60-minute uptake period of rest, patients were imaged with the PET/CT imaging system. First, a CT (120 kV, 80 mA, 0.8-s rotation time, slice thickness 3.75 mm) was performed from the base of the skull to the mid-thigh. PET scanning was performed immediately after the acquisition of the CT. Images were acquired from the base of the skull to the mid-thigh (3 min/bed position). PET images were reconstructed by using an ordered-subset expectation maximization iterative reconstruction (OSEM) (two iterations, 28 subsets) and an iterative fully 3D (DiscoveryST). CT data were used for attenuation calculation.

6) CHUP:

PET/CT acquisition began after 6 hours of fasting and 60 ± 5 min after injection of 3 MBq/kg of 18F-FDG (421 ± 98 MBq, range 220-695 MBq). Non-contrast-enhanced, non-respiratory gated (free breathing) CT images were acquired for attenuation correction (120 kVp, Care Dose® current modulation system) with an in-plane resolution of $0.853 \times 0.853 \text{ mm}^2$ and a 5 mm slice thickness. PET data were acquired using 2.5 minutes per bed position routine protocol, and images were reconstructed using a CT-based attenuation correction and the OSEM-TrueX-TOF algorithm (with time-of-flight and spatial resolution modeling, 3 iterations and 21 subsets, 5 mm 3D Gaussian post-filtering, voxel size $4 \times 4 \times 4 \text{ mm}^3$).

7) MDA:

For the PET portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median of 401 MBq (range: 327-266) was injected intravenously. After a 90-minute uptake period of rest, patients were imaged with the PET/CT imaging system. Image acquisition of the head and neck was performed using multiple bed positions with a median of 180 s (range: 90-300) per bed position. Attenuation-corrected images were reconstructed using an ordered subset expectation maximization (OSEM) iterative algorithm (2 iterations, 18-24 subsets, 5mm Gaussian filter). The median FDG-PET slice thickness was 3.27 mm (range: 2.99-5), and the median in-plane resolution was $5.46 \times 5.46 \text{ mm}^2$ (range: 2.73×2.73 - 5.46×5.46). For the CT portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, a median energy of 120 kVp (range: 100-140) with a median exposure of 185 mAs (range: 10-397) was used. The median CT slice thickness resolution was 3.75mm (range: 2.99-5), and the median in-plane resolution was $0.98 \times 0.98 \text{ mm}^2$ (range: 0.48×0.48 - 2.734×2.734).

8) USZ:

For PET imaging, an activity of 178–513 MBq was administered intravenously 1h prior to the scan and after measuring blood sugar level. In the retrospective cohort, 2D or 3D iterative image reconstruction was used, whereas the images of the validation cohort were reconstructed with a 3D algorithm.

9) CHB:

Head and neck PET-CT images were acquired on a GE710 PET-CT device (General Electric, Milwaukee, USA) 90 minutes (± 5 min) after injecting approximately 3 MBq/kg of FDG. PET and CT acquisition parameters were adapted to the patient's habitus with the patient in the radiotherapy treatment position with a contention mask. For the unenhanced CT portion of the FDG-PET/CT scan, an energy of 120 kVp with an exposure of 25 mAs was used. Attenuation-corrected images were reconstructed using an ordered subset expectation maximization (OSEM) iterative algorithm (VPFX, 2 iterations, and 23 subsets) and a span (axial mash) of 5. The FDG-PET slice thickness resolution was 3.27 mm for all patients, and the median in-plane resolution was 2.73×2.73 mm². The CT slice thickness resolution was 2.5 mm, and the median in-plane resolution was 0.98×0.98 mm² for all patients.

10) CHUN:

After 6h fasting; 3MBq/kg; Acquisition 60 min post-injection; contrast agent if possible, acquisition steps adapted to patient's morphology

Siemens Biograph mCT: Data were reconstructed using the 3D ordinary Poisson ordered subset expectation maximization algorithm with point spread function recovery and time-of-flight information. The reconstruction parameters were 3 iterations, 21 subsets with a 2-mm full width at half maximum (FWHM) Gaussian post-filtering (voxel size $4 \times 4 \times 2$ mm³). Low-dose CT 3D was acquired for attenuation and scatter correction, with or without intravenous contrast enhancement, and automatic mA according to the patient's weight.

Siemens Biograph Vision 450: Data were reconstructed using the 3D ordinary Poisson ordered subset expectation maximization algorithm with point spread function recovery and time-of-flight information. The reconstruction parameters were 4 iterations and 5 subsets with a 3-mm FWHM Gaussian post-filtering for the Biograph Vision 450 (voxel size $1.65 \times 1.65 \times 1.65$ mm³). Low-dose CT 3D was acquired for attenuation and scatter correction, with or without intravenous contrast enhancement, and automatic mA according to the patient's weight.

11) HUG:

After fasting for 6h, all patients had a single [18F]FDG injection, followed by a PET/MRI and a subsequent PET/CT scan. A mean dose of 373 ± 28 MBq [18F]FDG was injected intravenously into all patients before the PET/MRI examination was started. During the time necessary for radiotracer uptake, a dedicated MRI of the HN region (T2-weighted, diffusion-weighted, and T1-weighted sequences before and after iv. administration of a gadolinium-based contrast material), followed by total body MRI sequences was performed. The total body MRI sequences (see below) were used for attenuation correction, lesion detection, anatomic localization, and lesion characterization. Afterward, a whole-body PET was acquired on the PET/MRI system. The patient was then transferred to the PET/CT scanner, and no additional [18F]FDG was injected. PET/CT images were acquired on a Biograph 64 True Point scanner (Siemens Healthcare, Erlangen, Germany). The standard dose CT scan used for attenuation correction and diagnosis (with soft tissue, bone, and lung windows) had the following parameters: 120kVp, 180mAs, pitch = 1.2, collimation = 24×1.5 , 1 s per rotation, reconstructed CT slice thickness = 2 mm, reconstruction interval = 1.5 mm. PET data acquisition was started 120 ± 21 min after injection of [18F]FDG with a total of 8–9 bed positions. The delay between the end of the PET acquisition on the PET/MRI machine and the start of the PET acquisition on the PET/CT machine was, on average, 26 min. No iodine-based iv. contrast material was administered because: (1) according to the ESUR guidelines, for patients with a normal or moderately reduced GFR, there should be ≥ 4 h between injections of gadolinium- and iodine-based contrast agents [25]; (2) current guidelines for PET/CT do not recommend the routine use of iv. iodine-based contrast in all PET/CT examinations.

The AWOSEM iterative reconstruction algorithm (4 iterations, 8 subsets, voxel size = $4 \times 4 \times 5$ mm³) was applied for PET reconstruction. Standardized uptake values (SUVs) were calculated separately for PET/MRI and PET/CT according to the standard formula.

12) CHUB: Details to collect (standard clinical protocol)

13) GORTEC: Details to collect (standard clinical protocol)

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

These are the list of centers that are confirmed:

- HGJ: Hôpital général juif, Montréal, CA
- CHUS: Centre hospitalier universitaire de Sherbrooke, Sherbrooke, CA
- HMR: Hôpital Maisonneuve-Rosemont, Montréal, CA
- CHUM: Centre hospitalier de l'Université de Montréal, Montréal, CA
- CHUV: Centre Hospitalier Universitaire Vaudois, CH
- CHUP: Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Poitiers, FR
- CHUN: Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Nantes, FR
- HUG: Hôpitaux Universitaires de Genève, CH
- GORTEC: Multiple French/Swiss centers, details currently being collected

These centers were included in the 2022 edition and have shown interest in joining the 2025 challenge, but we are waiting for the final approvals:

- MDA: MD Anderson Cancer Center, Houston, Texas, USA
- CHB: Centre Henri Becquerel, Rouen, FR
- USZ: UniversitätsSpital Zürich, CH
- CHUB: Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Brest, FR

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

None.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Training and testing cases represent one 3D FDG-PET volume registered with a 3D CT volume of the head and neck region, as well as contours with the annotated ground truth lesions (only available for training cases to the participating teams). The labels will have three values: background with the value 0, primary Gross Tumor Volumes (GTVp) with the value 1, and nodal Gros Tumor Volumes (GTVn) with the value 2 (in case of several lymph nodes, they are considered all with the same label). Patient information including center, age, gender, tobacco and alcohol consumption, performance status, HPV status, treatment (radiotherapy only or chemoradiotherapy) and M stage are also included with each case although some variables are not available for all patients.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The total number of cases should be more than 1500 from at least 15 centers (the GORTEC cohort is multicentric, and we should get datasets from at least 3 centers within it). The total number of training cases is approximately 850 from 9 different centers. No specific validation cases are provided, and the training set can be split in any manner for cross-validation. The test cases of the 2022 challenge will be moved to the 2023 training set. The total number of test cases should be approximately 700 from at least six centers, consisting of new and previously unseen cases (none are publicly available).

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

For this new edition, we include new data from at least six additional centers (a multicentric cohort GORTEC with several hundreds of patients from a dozen centers, from which we should be able to collect around 300 patients from at least 3 centers, CHUB, CHUN, and HUG). The training set will comprise public and non-public data, whereas the test set will only include non-public data. There will be a total of at least 15 centers providing data. The training set will contain more diversity in centers (9) than the test set (at least 6).

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

Training and test cohorts are representative of the distribution of the real-world population of patients accepted for initial staging of oropharyngeal cancer.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

HECKTOR 2025 will incorporate new, unpublished data through four entirely new cohorts joining the consortium. These include one multicentric cohort (GORTEC) and centers from France and Switzerland, contributing approximately 400 previously unseen cases that will constitute the test set. This new data represents roughly 27% of the total challenge database of over 1,500 patients, with the remaining ~850 cases from previous HECKTOR data serving as the training set.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

HPV status obtained in patients' records.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if

necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

No specific instructions. The patients' outcomes were collected and recorded in the patient's records at the last follow-up. The patient's HPV status was collected and recorded in the patient's records.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Not applicable.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Not applicable.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Same as Task 1 for the images and contours. No preprocessing of the HPV status is required.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter- and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

N/A

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Balanced accuracy (average of sensitivity and specificity).

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Binary classification in the context of imbalanced configurations requires balanced accuracy (compared to the standard definition of accuracy).

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

The rankings will be based on the balanced accuracy value obtained in the test cohort. The participant with the highest accuracy wins. In the case of ties, the best specificity wins. The clear tiebreaker protocol using specificity ensures deterministic ranking even in the unlikely event of identical balanced accuracy scores. This approach ensures fair ranking even with imbalanced test sets.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

In the unlikely event of missing results on the test case, it will be considered misclassified to compute the overall balanced accuracy.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

Balanced accuracy suits binary classification tasks and can appropriately rank the diagnostic models to classify patients as HPV+ or HPV-. In case of ties, we will favor models with higher specificity, which is more clinically relevant, as de-escalation of patients could be envisioned for HPV+ patients with a more favorable prognosis, at the condition of high specificity, to avoid de-escalation of patients needing it.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

A bootstrap will be performed on the test set to evaluate the variance of the C-index of each team and for statistical comparison of algorithm results. The Python SciPy and Scikit-learn libraries will be used for the statistical analyses.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The bootstrap analysis allows us to simulate different sampling of the test set to approximate the variance of the C-index.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

A consensus of the best models will be evaluated using the C-index to establish whether there is complementary value for prognosis. Similarly to Task 1, we will compare the results obtained on the different centers of the test

set.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

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Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A